

CULTURAL INFLUENCES ON MARKETING AND ADVERTISING STRATEGIES**Prof. Nitin A.Taware***Ph.D Scholar Shri JJT University. Assistant Professor, Faculty of Fine Arts (Applied Arts) Pune.**Dr. D.Y. Patil College of Applied Art & Crafts, Akurdi, Pune-44***Abstract**

The purpose is to explore how Cultural Influences on Marketing and advertising Strategies Growing companies are always looking for new opportunities. Some of these opportunities are in the new country, while others are in the country. In India either case, focusing on specific cultural groups can open up new markets for your company. Product diversification and growth may require product launches on a global scale. In order to develop a successful marketing strategy, an organization must consider the social cultural impact of introducing new products. People decide the consumption of products based on these cultural influences.

"Marketing covers those activities that relate the organization to those parts of the outside world that use, buy, sell or influence the output it produces and the benefits and services it offers" The company uses a marketing method on a global scale, the so-called international marketing method, which basically allocates resources without considering national boundaries. The company seeks profits worldwide through international marketing, systems and plans. Products are designed according to customer needs in specific countries/regions, and country/region-based promotions will be carried out in international marketing

Advertising is a marketing tool and paid form of communication designed to pursue consumers. Advertising has three basic functions. Basically, it informs consumers of new products. The "persuasiveness" function of advertising is actually an attempt to convince consumers to buy products. As far as the "reminder" function of the advertisement is concerned, it helps to remind consumers of information about the product, so that customers do not have to buy products from competitors' brands and remember the product. Cultural value is an integral part of the consumer's self, not an environmental factor. Consumers' needs and demands change rapidly over time, and marketers should strive to identify consumers' changing needs in order to better understand consumers' buying behavior. The first step is to understand the audience and then design ads to attract target customers. Therefore, it's important to understand the "buyer's decision-making process"

Keywords : *Marketing and advertising Strategies, communication designs, International Marketing Strategy, Consumer Psychographic, Consumer behaviors and Cultures.*

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Introduction

This paper mainly studies the spread of modern technology on a global scale, including information and communication technology (ICT), is generally regarded as both a sign of the post-modern era of globalization and a close interaction between humans, goods, services, information and capital. Some international marketers predict that culturally different markets will eventually merge into "One World Culture", which will promote global standardized marketing activities (Levitt, 1983). However, facts have proved that this is an illusion-many non-cultural hard factor and cultural soft factors still exist or appear. This is a restriction on international marketing, and various adaptation or localization strategies must be used to continuously respond.

Culture has a profound impact on customers' product choices, motivations and lifestyles. Cultural influence is reflected by how many customers prefer to buy the same product. Due to the growth of international trade, product marketing strategies need to be redesigned. Culture has a huge impact on global marketing. Culture refers to the influence of religion, family, education and social systems on people, their lifestyles and the choices they make.

Marketing always exists in an environment shaped by culture. Culture has a great influence on international marketing. Marketers must research the local culture in depth before offering them products. Since every marketing activity carried out a promotion to promote the product, that is, to communicate with customers about product features and influence customers to purchase products.

They promote choice and only reflect existing cultural values. In fact, advertising not only expands the market share, but also expands the market size. ...Although it reflects society to a certain extent, it also has the function of "regulating" value or behavior when a small business chooses to promote to the international market, it will face a series of unique challenges. Although the company undoubtedly wants to maintain a consistent image in different markets, it must also consider the cultural background into which its marketing materials enter. In the United States, such as in Sudan, the information received may vary. Therefore, even a small company should standardize its marketing internationally, but still have room for flexibility.

Literature review:-

Marieke de Mooij global, (2005); analysed the various components of culture that influence the marketing programs. There has always been a debate over the problems being faced by the managers to make an appropriate strategy for marketing. There is always influence of culture on the marketing mix due to the change in the needs of consumers because of cultural diversification

(De Mooij, Hofstede: 2011). Discussing about social process steering consumer behaviors contains emotions and motivations and is bounded by cultures and variation in motives helps for development of advertisement appeals across cultures. Psychologists argue that Emotions (anger, fear, sadness, joy) are universal however the use of these emotions, meanings and intensity of the emotions vary according to specific cultures. According to study East Asian cultures tend to display positive emotions only e.g. joy and happiness.

Huib Wursten and Tom Fadrhonc,(2012), indicated that the marketers who were expanding their boundaries and are trading with other countries face a real problem of a perfect marketing mix for their products. It becomes very difficult for the management to follow an approach which is according to the differences in cultures of the countries. They explained the theory of cultural dimensions. The various researches have come to the conclusion that there are five areas which describe the cultural diversification for strategies of marketing.

Gabriela capatina (2014), analyzed that framing marketing programs at international market are one of the complex decisions that the management has to make. He considered many factors like Investment decisions, Human resource decision and marketing mix decisions in cultural context. The paper represented that success of new product launch depends upon marketing program in cultural framework. He also describes future directions that management should consider cultural differences between various groups while deciding marketing programs.

This section will provide relevant studies and theories related to culture, Communication and advertisements along with conceptual framework for thesis.

Objective: -

The purpose of this article is to determine cultural factors and study the influence of cultural factors on product promotion marketing strategies. If all cultural strategies are based on their plans, these cultural factors can be actively used.

Scope: - Growing companies are always looking for new opportunities. Some of these opportunities are in the new country, while others are in the country. In either case, focusing on specific cultural groups can open up new markets for your company. Product diversification and growth may require product launches on a global scale.

Research methodology:-

- the paper is descriptive and analytical in nature.
- This article attempts to analyze the Cultural Influences on Marketing and advertising Strategies
- According to research needs, my research is completely based on secondary data

Culture marketing-

Culture marketing is a form of content marketing that showcases your culture to help people get to know your brand. ... Example: To give people a behind-the-scenes look at its company culture, Zappos created the Culture Book, an in-depth look at the people, values, and practices that make the company unique.

Influence of advertising: -

Advertising Influences Consumer Behavior At its core, the influence of advertising in everyday life is the power to alter what consumers think and feel. A successful ad cultivates desire within the viewer and makes her want to buy a product while minimizing any doubts she has about the product.

Advertising influence consumer behavior: -

Advertising promotes social messages and life style through illustrating the position of ideal consumer and stimulates social action toward purchase of that product. Advertising spending also creates positive impression about a brand in the minds of the consumers.

Consumer behaviors and Cultures:-

The process involved in consumer behavior is defined by De Mooij as "the study of the process involved in people choosing, buying, using, and disposing of products, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy needs and desires (DeMooij2010: P 93). The various components of this process are shown in the figure below:

Global Advertising Research: Understanding Cultural values of Consumer

Figure 02-CONSUMER BEHAVIOR - ECLAIRS | Consumer motivation.

Figure 01-Cross-cultural consumer behavior model Source:

Everyone in society has the concept of "self", which is about our current personality and the image of the personality we want to be. The notions of self, identity and image are connected with the notion of self. Cultural value plays a very important role in consumer self-concept. The individualistic culture regards the concept of self as an "autonomous entity". Everyone has unique qualities, attributes or processes, and behavior is developed according to the configuration of these attributes. For example, in an individualistic society, young people develop their own identities and can operate independently of their families in the society; while in a collectivist culture, identities are developed by encouraging dependence, and there are very complicated complex relationships.

And regulations, while collectivist culture is classified according to the relationship between objects. Information processing varies with individualism/collectivism and power distance. In a culture of high-power alienation and collectivism, people tend to obtain information through implicit communication, and they tend to buy products based on trust in the company and feelings, while in a culture of low-power alienation and individualism, people tend to use friends and the media to obtain information to make a purchase. The automatic and frequent flow of information caused by social interaction and knowledge is obtained unconsciously, and "information" is related to low-context, individualism and low-power remote culture (Hofstede, De Mooij: 2010) Due to the poor interaction of traditional art teaching Method, efficiency of use of art teaching resources low. To solve the problem, interact Applying visual thinking to reform traditional art teaching method. Due to the interactive virtual tour in the simulation Scenes based on virtual reality technology with characteristics Multi-sensory, interactive, immersive and autonomous Etc., widely used in structural exhibitions, personnel Operation training, product structure design verification.

Standardization or local adjustment of global marketing strategies:-

Today, global marketing has become the main idea of scholars and practitioners. Some people believe that the global market has become homogeneous. Multinational companies can use the same strategy to sell standardized products and

services around the world, thereby reducing costs and increasing profits (Subash, 1989). Levitt (1983) first supported this standardization strategy in a homogeneous market in an article in "Harvard Business Review". Levitt believes that marketers face a "homogeneous global village." He suggested organizing the development of standardized high-quality world products, and using standardized advertising, pricing and distribution for global marketing. Moreover, through standardization, companies can obtain the benefits of economies of scale in procurement, logistics, production and marketing. In addition, they can transfer management expertise, and all of this should ultimately lead to lower prices. It is said that standardization also provides the possibility of establishing a unified global company image, a world brand or a global brand with a global image. With a relatively small number of strong global brand portfolios, companies may wish to achieve greater marketing effects. Supporters of Levitt's theory talked about the development of powerful advertising across international borders, involving all aspects of culture, nationality, race, religion, values and customs.

Cross-cultural marketing communication-communication theory:-

Figure -03- Marketing Communication process

An effective marketing communication model includes sender, receiver, and message, which are connected to each other through channels, and messages may be distorted by scattered stimuli (noise). Perception is shared through marketing communications. This perception can only be successful when the sender and receiver's perception fields are consistent with each other.

As shown in the model, the sender, receiver and message are connected through a message channel. The communication process should start with the merchant asking the potential customer/recipient in advance. The sender should study the characteristics of the receiver used to deliver the message. In order to make it easy for the receiver to understand, the conversion of the message into the symbol form is the encoding. The message channel is the way to send the message to the receiver, and the decoding is the process of message symbol conversion in the mind. In a successful communication process, the sender and receiver's responses to needs overlap, which shows that the communication process has worked. Noise is an intrusive stimulus that interferes with accurate message reception. For international marketers, understanding cultural noise is very important (Czinkota & Ronkainen 2007). Perceived coding and decoding gaps stem from differences between cultures.

The sender and receiver distort the communication between people in different cultural backgrounds. More and better information about target audiences, consumer behavior, purchasing power, buyers' cultural value and demographic behavior can lead to the development of better promotional strategies in international advertising. (Root, 1994).

There are four types of market segmentation:-

Although consumers can be grouped together by any characteristic, the following four parts are considered the richest description of how people buy. Population breakdown

- 1. Demographic segmentation** - the simplest and most widely used segmentation type, which can divide the purchase population by age, gender, income, occupation, family size, race, religion and nationality. For example, you can define the group as "males between the ages of 18 and 35, each year earns between 30,000 and 50,000 USD".
- 2. Behavioral segmentation** - Behavioral segmentation divides the population based on the population as customers' buying behavior. How often do they buy products? Are they early adopters, or are they waiting for the product to attract the masses before investing? How loyal are they to the product or brand?
- 3. Psychological segmentation**- Psychological segmentation is closely related to behavior, but this time we will study someone's lifestyle and opinions more carefully to define the target market. What are the consumer's political views? How environmentally conscious is he? Is he a party creature or an introvert? What activities does he like? What is his hobby? Understanding the impact of these lifestyles means you can customize your marketing campaigns so that they are more specific to the motivations of your customers.
- 4. Geographic segmentation** - Dividing people based on their place of residence is called geographic segmentation. Your customers will have different needs based on their location: rural and urban, big cities and small towns, hot countries and cold countries, etc. You may not sell many air conditioners to customers living in Iceland, but there is still room for growth in the southern Spanish market!

International marketing strategy:-

International marketing is the application of marketing principles to meet the diverse needs of different people across national borders. In short, the International Marketing Department should carry out marketing activities in more than one country. E.g As you can imagine, international marketing is the marketing of products or services in multiple countries. Some products or services can only be sold locally, while other products or services can be sold anywhere. ...Red Bull is a great example of international marketing – it's easy to forget that they are an Austrian company. Four international strategies are these two aspects have produced four basic global business strategies: export, standardization, multinational and transnational. As shown below. International business strategies must strike a balance between local responsiveness and global integration.

Consumer Psychographic:-

If you have ever wondered why customers act like this-then you are already thinking about psychological issues. This marketing concept aims to divide customers into categories based on their psychological or lifestyle characteristics. If done correctly, psychoanalysis can answer the following questions:-Why do consumers choose product A instead of product B? Why does this product have a higher brand value in the eyes of customers? Which marketing messages will match the customer's life values?

Finding- results and discussion :-

The purpose of this research is to analyze and clarify once you have determined the cultural group you want to target, study their behavior, attitude and buying habits. Customer surveys and feedback cards can help you determine which aspects of the products and services your target audience likes most. Read magazines that target cultural groups and visit websites they frequently visit. Visit successful competitors and learn how they monitor and take advantage of cultural changes.

Use the information you collect to design ads that match the cultural attitudes of potential customers. If possible, hire an advertising company that specializes in marketing for the specific cultural group you are after. For example, a retail business that targets young people may benefit from the services of a marketing company that specializes in street promotions for young people.

After analyzing all factors and their impact on culture, it is clear that the management team must consider cultural differences between different groups of people when deciding on product promotion strategies. In future research, the influence of socioeconomic variables on cultural dimensions should be considered. The problem facing researchers is data availability. Due to cultural diversity, it is difficult for researchers to study all cultures, and it is also difficult for marketers to analyze which product a group of people prefer. Even people living in the same society have different religions, customs, and traditions, so marketers cannot judge that customers in a geographic area have the same choices. The previous education level can also be included in future research, especially to reveal the cultural superiority of socio-economic factors over a long period of time. This method can also be used to analyze the impact of various marketing variables and their interrelationships with other cultural and socio-economic factors. It is also important for marketers and researchers to evaluate which activities are most successful over a long period of time.

Conclusion: -

Marketing strategy for product promotion is one of them the most important decision for marketers the face of the company. Cultural diversity has increased Uncertainty and difficulty of taking Marketing plan decision. All marketing the strategy is formulated after studying the corporate culture Specific groups, because each group has a different According to their income, customs and needs Tradition. Culture has many elements

Direct or indirect influence Marketing. An excellent marketer who wants to survive Products cannot ignore learning for a long time changing cultural needs. So international The marketer must analyze what he offers Who is his product for and what is their culture background. Varies due to diversity there are different cultural behaviors all over the world, Customs, tastes and norms. Marketers must after studying all of these, promote their products factor. In terms of conclusions, marketing International market strategy is considered become a predictor of future product growth At the same time, a valuable distribution method Marketing attempts.

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